

From Underdeveloped to Innovation Learners: Case of sub-Saharan African countries and lesson for MENA countries

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Abstract:

In the latest decades, the innovation takes an important place in the growth of the economy. In this paper, we will try to answer the questions: what are the important characteristics that make the Sub-Saharan countries innovation learner? At first, we find that creating a strong innovation system is the important key to innovate. Second, investing in human capital appear also as an important factor that lead these African countries to be innovators. In the end, we try to find the place of the MENA countries from these characteristics and giving some recommendation to catch up the innovation learners.

Keywords: GII (Global Innovation Index), Innovation, Africa, MENA.

Jel classification codes : O3, O55.

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Introduction:

Following the different changes in the world, the growth in the technology, the scarce sources of energy are from the important factors that push the different countries in the world to use latest technologies, to follow different methods to survive. From these changes, the innovation appears, that is using existing sources in different way to produce more or using other sources of energy. Following the results gathered after these changes, different companies find that it is so important to implement the innovation as an important factor for surviving with the existing sources in addition to grow up with the competitiveness level and the wealth of the nation. With the huge changes after the appearance of the innovation, we demonstrate that all economies follow to innovate but there are some who stay in the top of the rank for Five years, where other decline because of the political instability and other indefinite variables. From the unexpected results, the Sub-Saharan countries accounts from the innovation learners. Following the (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014), the Sub-Saharan Africa now accounts for almost 50% of countries with the status of “innovation learner” more than other regions, the latest data present that from the seventh, five of the Sub-Saharan Africa countries show rising levels of innovation. Therefore, in the beginning of this paper, we will give a quick overview about the different definition of the innovation; in the second step identify the global innovation index. After, we try to demonstrate the key element of being innovation learners, especially for the sub-Saharan¹ countries, and what the fail points for the MENA countries with some actual data. In the end, we conclude with some important recommendation following the studies in addition to the schedules followed in the other countries.

1. Theoretical background:

1.1. Definition of innovation:

Nowadays and with the technological changes every second, we find that the most important element is the innovation process because it is the important driver for the economic progress and competitiveness for both developed and developing economies (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 41). Following the different studies about innovation, it takes different faces, for that it is necessary to give a fix definition about it. Following the definition cited in (OECD 2005, 15, 151), “innovation is a continuous process ...it is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good, service), or process, or a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, a workplace organization, or external relations”. According to (OECD 2005, 15), the innovation is defined as a continuous process in different domain. The Chief Executive Officer of Alcatel-lucent Mr. Ben Verwaayen said:” Innovation has always been an important element in the relative success of

¹ **The Sub-Saharan countries are** : Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Rep., Chad, Comoros, Congo, Côte d’Ivoire, Dem. Rep. of the Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Seychelles, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, South Sudan, Swaziland, Togo
Uganda, United Rep. of Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe

societies—economically, intellectually, and socially “(Soumitra Dutta 2011). According to (Rennings 2000), “the source of innovation is the Latin word *Novus* which means new. It is referred sometimes as new idea, new method or new device or the process of creating something new. Following the different studies about the definition of the innovation, it is a “broad concept which encompass a wide range of activities and processes: markets, entrepreneurship, networks and competition, but also skills and organizations, creativity and knowledge transfers”(OECD 2009, 11) Following the definition of the EIU (economic intelligence unity),’ the innovation is the application of knowledge in a novel way, primarily for economic benefits. According to the important role of innovation in the economy and following the studies of (Soumitra Dutta 2010, 6), from the extraordinary capacities of the innovation for the economic growth in general are facilitating the countries recovery in addition to sustaining the national competitiveness in the short and long run. However, following the different changes in the environment that face the different enterprises, it force them to look for ways of improving quality and reputation, efficiency and increasing the market share. From the different approach to improve, the competitive advantage of the enterprise is innovation. According to (Yeung 2006), the innovation development is from the important strategic drivers to achieve the competitiveness and the productivity. From the important goals related with the importance of studying innovation is to better understand innovation and its role in the economic growth (OECD 2005, 14). Following its importance, we touched it in the different sector as we find in the latest studies, there is a an important focus in the role of the innovation in the tourism sector(Thomas and Wood 2014).

Innovation Learners are economies that perform at least 10% higher than expected for their level of GDP (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 11)

Innovation Leaders: are the states that follow the same schedule but there bet the top of the rank. We find that Switzerland is the top of the innovation leader for four years due to the mixture used to keep this place.

1.2. **Innovation Efficiency Ratio:**

Before defining the innovation efficiency ratio, it is important to give definition for the innovation efficiency. Following (Hollanders and Celikel-Esser 2007, 4), Innovation efficiency can be defined as the ability of firms to translate innovation inputs into innovation outputs. Innovation efficiency is improved when with the same amount of innovation inputs more innovation outputs are generated or when less innovation inputs are needed for generating the same amount of innovation outputs. For the IER, it is related to the concept of productivity. it can be calculated as the total of innovation outputs, such as (firm turnover coming from new products, employment in high tech sectors, patents, trademarks, designs etc.), over the total innovation inputs such as (education, investment in innovation, innovation activities at the firm level, etc.) (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 12), It shows how much innovation output a given country is getting for its inputs.

1.3. **Global Innovation Index GII:**

Following (Soumitra Dutta 2007, 29), the global innovation index GII was conceived at INSEAD as a formal model to help show the degree to which individual nations and regions currently respond to the challenge of innovation. It

is intended in the first to serve as a mean of determining a country’s relative response capacity, to give a clear picture of its strengths and deficiencies in respect to innovation-related policies and practices and to find metrics and approaches that better capture the richness of the innovation in the society and go beyond such traditional measures of innovation as the number of research articles and the level of research and development expenditures. Due to the different relations of the innovation with the other sectors, in addition to the bilateral effect between innovation and other sectors, it is necessary to include different sectors. For that, we find that GII include different pillars that touch different sectors from the politics to business. The figure below captures the different pillars of GII:

Figure 1: Framework of the Global Innovation Index 2014

Source: (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 8)

We can identify that the innovation is a result after the mixture of different sectors and pillars, i.e. the country or the company follow a schedule characterized in inputs and we get the innovation results as outputs. There for, you will find that the framework is divided into inputs and out puts.

1.4. Calculating the GII:

Following the study of (Soumitra Dutta 2007, 2), the Global Innovation Index for any given country is calculated in the following manner:

1. The values of each variable for the country are scaled on a range of 1 to 7.
2. The values of all variables for the country under a particular pillar are averaged to yield a score from 1 to 7 for that pillar for the country.
3. The scores of all five Input pillars are averaged to give an overall score (on a scale of 1 to 7) of the country for the Input dimension.
4. The scores of all three Output pillars are averaged to give an overall score (on a scale of 1 to 7) of the country for the Output dimension.
5. The overall Input and Output scores (steps 3 and 4 respectively above) are averaged to yield the overall Global Innovation Index score (on a range of 1 to 7) for the country.

2. Exploratory study:

2.1. Innovation in the world:

The ability to innovate is related directly with the level of income for the country. Following the previous factors of the GII, the countries with high-level income are more innovative than the countries with middle income and so on. In addition, we find that all countries in different level of income has the highest rates in the institutions. Where, there is few declines in the other factors such as human capital and research.

Figure 2: The persistent innovation divide: Stability among the top 10 and top 25

From the figure in left, we find a good classification between the level of income and the score of innovation. There for, we can estimate the positive relationship between the level of income in the country and their ability to innovate.

Source: (Dutta, Lanvin, and Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 10)

2.2. The top tenth ranked countries from 2011 to 2014:

From the data gathered, we found there are different changes in the ranks following different changes in the different factors included in the GII calculation. The figure below presents the changes in the ten top innovators following the GII data.

Table 1: movement in the top 10 of the GII countries2007-2015

	2007	2008-2009	2009-2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
rank	country	Country	Country	Country	country	Country	country	country
1	USA	USA	Iceland	Switzerla nd	Switzerla nd	Switzerla nd	Switzerlan d	Switzerlan d
2	Germany	Germany	Sweden	Sweden	Sweden	Sweden	UK	UK
3	UK	Sweden	Hong	Singapore	Singapore	UK	Sweden	Sweden

			Kong, China					
4	Japan	UK	Switzerla nd	Hong Kong	Finland	Netherlan ds	Finland	Netherlan ds
5	France	Singapore	Denmark	Finland	UK	USA	Netherlan ds	USA
6	Switzerla nd	Korea, south	Finland	Denmark	Netherlan ds	Finland	USA	Finland
7	Singapore	Switzerla nd	Singapore	USA	Denmark	Hong Kong	Singapore	Singapore
8	Canada	Denmark	Netherlan ds	Canada	Hong Kong	Singapore	Denmark	Ireland
9	Netherlan ds	Japan	New Zealand	Netherlan ds	Ireland	Denmark	Luxembou rg	Luxembou rg
10	Hong Kong	Netherlan ds	Norway	UK	USA	Ireland	Hong Kong	Denmark

Source: edited by the author using the GII reports 2007-2015

The table above include the movement of the top ten of the GII countries where we find that in 2015, the Switzerland is in the top of the list for the Fifth time, in the second place we see the United Kingdom for the second time in the second place and the Sweden in the third place for the second time also (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2015, 11). The top 10 economies in the GII 2014 edition are Switzerland, the UK, Sweden, Finland, the Netherlands, the USA, Singapore, Denmark, Luxembourg, and Hong Kong (China). Nine of these economies were already in the GII top 10 in 2013; Ireland, which was in the top 10 in 2013, dropped to 11th place this year, and Luxembourg climbed up into the top 10 from 12th position in 2013. In addition, we find that the United Kingdom jump from the 10th place in 2011 to the 5th place in 2012, and it continued the growth to take the place 3 in 2013. The last year, it takes the second place after Switzerland. This biggest jump clarifies the best policies to enhance innovation.

2.3. The highest jump in the GII ranking from 2012 to 2013:

According to the growth of the importance of innovation in the daily life of people. The different state launched different procedures to foster it, for that, we find the changes in the ranking every year. The biggest changes are founded in 2012-2013 where many countries jump with more than 15 places. The tables below demonstrate the biggest jumps between 2012-2013

We found that Uganda in the top of big jumping in the period 2012-2013 following

Table 2: biggest jumps in the GII rankings from 2012 to 2013

Country	GII 2012 rank	GII 2013 rank	Jump
Uganda	117	89	28
Cost Arica	60	39	21
Bolivia	114	95	19
Cambodia	129	110	19
Mexico	79	63	16
Uruguay	67	52	15
Indonesia	100	85	15
Ecuador	98	83	15

the procedures follows. For example, UNICEF Uganda, through a unique Technology for Development unit, is working closely with the Government and partners to develop and implement innovative solutions to keep children alive, safe, and learning.

In addition, the innovations aim to help young Ugandans realize their right to

Table 3: The innovation leaders in Middle East and Africa 2007

Middle East			Africa		
Rank	Country	Score	Rank	Country	Score
14	UAE	3,81	38	South Africa	2,89
18	Israel	3,68	72	Nigeria	2,27
30	Kuwait	3,14	78	Kenya	2,22
41	Tunisia	2,84	79	Namibia	2,21

Source: (Dutta, 17 Jan 07, 21)

the importance of innovation in all sectors. Turning back to the essence of the paper that is related with the Sub-Saharan Africa and the MENA countries. The table 3 present the innovation leader from Africa and MENA countries in 2007. United Arab Emirates take the first place in the region due to the growth in different sector such as technology and education. In second place, Israel using the US technology. However, for the African countries, south Africa is the first innovation leader due to the foreign investment in the region that is lead to technology transfer. This latest enhance the levels of the different sectors such as education, industry, tourism ...etc.

2.4. Innovation for special areas:

Following (Ahmad Bin Byat and Osman Sultan 2014, 101), The United Arab Emirates (UAE) is quickly transforming itself from an oil-based economy to an innovative, knowledge-based economy. The launched the UAE’s *vision 2021*, which aims to build a nation where ‘knowledgeable and innovative Emiratis will confidently build a competitive and resilient economy. According the important role of the start-up in the innovation, we try to measure the innovation level by the number of the start-ups between the years 2012 and 2015. We find that in the MENA countries, the number of star-ups grow with 360 star-up in three years, tis growth is with 271 without the UAE.

participation and are one-step forward in ensuring transparency and accountability at the grassroots level.². From this table, we can confirm that all states care about

² <http://www.unicef.org/uganda/innovations.html>

Figure 3: Number of tech start-up in MENA (2012-2015)

From the chart in left , we can guess a best innovative future in the MENA region. Therefore, and to foster the innovation more and more, the government of UAE build strong bases for innovation based of three big pillars as it shown in the figure below.

These pillars are: Human capital, Financial capital and Technological capital.
 Source:(Dutta, Lanvin, and Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 108)

2.5. The innovation learners in Africa:

From the latest information gathered about the innovation learners, five of the sub-Saharan Africa countries that show rising levels of innovation (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 11). The **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** contain the ranks of some sub-Saharan Africa countries. Following the data gathered in addition to the different procedures and policies launched by the countries,

Table 4: ranking of innovation learners in Africa

GII ranking	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
GAMBIA	n/a	n/a	n/a	110	n/a	130	122	104
Burkina Faso	84	n/a	115	122	120	122	116	109
Rwanda	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	109	102	112	102
Malawi	n/a	n/a	n/a	97	108	120	119	113
Mozambique	103	n/a	125	100	n/a	110	121	107

Source: www.globalinnovationindex.org

The countries take different places. However, the countries selected in the table are the ones who are selected as the innovation learners for 2014 through the studies of (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014).

3. Cases from the sub-Saharan countries:

3.1 Rwanda:

Following the goals of the president Paul Kagame for making Rwanda the hub of its region (Soumitra Dutta 2007, 37), the government make different policies to achieve them. From the important ones we found that the government launched the Rwanda innovation endowment fund RIEF to fund R&D to foster innovative areas such as agriculture, manufacturing, ICTs, and energy, in partnership with the United Nation Economic Commission for Africa UNECA and One UN Rwanda. In addition, the Rwanda’s vision 2020 get a direct affect in the innovation through different procedures. One of the points that shows Rwanda’s growth, it was named the top performer in doing business 2010, having jumped 76 places from 143 to 67 in the annual ranking of 183 countries, the biggest improvement ever by any country. As a result of the government’s commitment to reform, it is now easier, faster, and less expensive to do business in Rwanda (Bank 2010). The World Bank launched two projects to supports the governments in its efforts and to improve the investment climates that are the CEDP³ project started by the IDA⁴ in 2001 in addition to the Rwanda Investment Climate Reform Program in 2007. The **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** below presents the GDP growth of Rwanda from 1960 to 2014. Following the figure, the GDP find stagnation in all period except a deterioration in 1994 because genocide against the Tutsi in Rwanda from April 7 to mid-July 1994. From the important factor that boosts the economic growth is the foreign direct investment. Therefore, the Figure 5 represents the participation of the FDI in Rwanda GDP growth. The foreign direct investment finds different steps in Rwanda from 1970 until nowadays. In the latest period, we find an important growth especially after 2010, these data clarify the big interest to invest in this area in the different field of investments such as agriculture, manufacturing and ICTs

Figure 4: Rwanda GDP growth (annual %) 1960- 2014 **Figure 5: Rwanda FDI net inflows (% of GDP) 1970-2014**

³ CEDP : Competitiveness and Enterprise Development Project
⁴ IDA: International Development Association

Therefore, the Figure 5 above represents the participation of the FDI in Rwanda GDP growth:

The foreign direct investment finds different steps in Rwanda from 1970 until nowadays. In the latest period, we find an important growth especially after 2010, these data clarify the big interest to invest in this area in the different field of investments such as agriculture, manufacturing and ICTs. The figure below clarifies the changes in different sectors in Rwanda:

Figure 6: Rwanda Agriculture added value as % of GDP 1965-2014 **Figure 7: Rwanda Manufacturing added value as % of GDP 1965-2014**

3.2 Gambia:

It has grown its ICT infrastructure and innovative service through various initiatives, and Gambia's ministry of Trade, industry, Regional integration and employment has also launched an innovation grant as part of the social development fund in order to commercialize local project. The regional projects

that foster innovation include CAID “the Children and Community Initiative for Development” and the AYP “the Africa Youth Panel” which have rolled out a range of capacity building initiatives for youth in the Sub-Saharan.

3.3 Burkina Faso:

From the important policies launched by Burkina Faso to foster innovation are⁵: The creation of the MSRI⁶ in January 16th, 2011 to foster the innovation, in addition to Research centers, universities, regional, African and international research. Launching the strategy of SCADD⁷ or AGSSD⁸. The Government of Burkina Faso has adopted in December 2012, a sectorial policy document of the Scientific and Technological Research (2013-2022). In December 2012 also, there is the adoption of a national strategy enhancement technologies, inventions and innovations in Burkina Faso. In December 2012 also, there is the adoption of a national strategy enhancement technologies, inventions and innovations in Burkina Faso. Launching the NPSRI⁹ for the socio-economic growth to achieve for innovative goals in the end of 2025. The creation of ANVAR¹⁰ and FRST¹¹

3.3 Malawi:

Malawi from the countries that are in the category of innovation learners through the different procedures followed during latest years. Malawi was from the many countries that are falling in poverty. Due to the creation of the IPA¹², they use the fingerprinting technology, this technology allows the IPA in the collaboration with MRFC¹³.

3.4 Mozambique:

The government star by using the technology because it is from the important drivers of innovation. From the policies applied by suing the technology is to start using the IT to improve the governance and public administration in addition to provide the citizens with benefits to access to the global knowledge bases.

4. Exploratory study of Innovation efficiency ratio:

4.1 The innovation efficiency ratio in the sub Saharan countries:

The innovation efficiency ratio is the rate that measure the innovation in the country, the ratio of outputs over inputs. In the table below, we try to give comparison between some Sub-Saharan Africa countries with other countries known with the level of technological development.

We find that the IER of Senegal and Kenya is over than the IER of India, the matter that it shows that these two countries start using

Figure 8: The innovation efficiency ratio

Countries	IER	Country	IER
Senegal	0,85	India	0,82
Kenya	0,84	Thailand	0,76
Gambia	0,76	Georgia	0,68

procedures to inter the innovation world. We find also that Gambia level is the same

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Source : <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org> table

¹⁰ National agency of Research Results Valuation

¹¹ National forum of scientific research and innovation

¹² Innovation of Poverty Action (<http://www.poverty-action.org>)

¹³ Malawi Rural Finance Corporation

as Thailand, there for, we can estimate that there is an important future for these countries in the field of innovation. The ECA «Economic Commission for Africa»¹⁴: it is a commission focusing on assisting African countries and Regional Economic Communities (RECs) in the formulation, adoption and implementation of new technology and innovation policies that will help them accelerate the transformation process to improve the competitiveness of their firms, the welfare of their citizens, including ensuring their collective and individual security. ECA also conducts research on national and regional innovation systems, technology transfer and on new and emerging technology likely to support economic transformation, and in key areas such as agriculture and social service delivery, where innovations and new technologies can support economic transformation and human resource development.

4.2 The IER “innovation efficiency ratio” for the MENA countries:

To give a clear picture of our paper, we try to gather the innovation learners form Sub-Saharan Africa countries and the MENA countries. The table below contain both categories of countries:

Figure 9: some data about the IER and the rank for MENA and Sub-Saharan African Countries

sub-Saharan Africa	Rank 2014	Rank 2013	IER/Rank	Innovation index/Rank	input	sub-innovation index/Rank	outputs	sub-
Gambia	104	122	0,8/58	32,9/111		25,1/93		
Burkina Faso	109	116	0,7/78	32,9/112		23,5/104		
Rwanda	102	112	0,5/137	40,2/74		18,4/128		
Malawi	113	119	0,7/96	33/109		22,2/108		
Mozambique	107	121	0,6/124	34,6/96		20,6/115		
MENA	Rank 2014	Rank 2013	IER/Rank	Innovation index/Rank	Input	sub-innovation index/Rank	outputs	sub-
Algeria	133	138	0,5/130	31,7/122		16,7/132		
Bahrain	62	67	0,6/117	45,5/48		27,1/80		
Egypt	99	108	0,8/59	34,1/104		26/89		
Iran	120	113	0,6/122	33,2/107		19/125		
Israel	15	14	0,8/42	61,8/17		49,1/13		
Jordan	64	61	0,8/40	40,3/72		32,1/57		
Kuwait	69	50	0,8/50	39,4/79		30,9/62		
Lebanon	77	75	0,6/119	42,2/61		25/95		
Morocco	84	92	0,7/83	38/89		26,5/86		
Oman	75	80	0,6/121	42,8/59		24,9/96		
Qatar	47	43	0,6/114	50,4/34		30,2/69		

¹⁴ <http://www.uneca.org/our-work/innovation-technology-0/pages/about-innovation-technology>

Saudi Arabia	38	42	0,7/70	47,8/39	35,4/41
Sudan	143	141	0,1/142	23,2/142	2,1/143
Tunisia	78	70	0,7/98	39,7/77	26,1/87
Turkey	54	68	0,9/11	39,7/78	36,7/39
UAE	36	38	0,5/127	56,2/25	30,3/68
Yemen	141	142	0,6/111	24,4/141	14,7/139

Source : <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org>

According to the table above, Sub-Saharan Africa is the region that sees the most significant improvement in GII rankings in 2014. The relative performance advantage of some of these nations is significant. Examples include Mauritius' high score in Institutions, South Africa's high score in Market Sophistication, Gambia's performance in Knowledge and Technology Outputs in addition to Seychelles' score in Creative Outputs. After calculating the GII score for all countries, by linking it in with the GDP in purchasing power parity, the different countries are segmented automatically in three categories with the trend line. As a result, the countries are segmented into two categories of countries:

The first category (The innovation learner): this group includes economies from the high and middle-income countries, such as: The Republic of Moldova, China, Mongolia, Viet Nam, India, Jordan, Armenia, Senegal, Malaysia, Thailand, Ukraine, and Georgia. They demonstrate rising levels of innovation results improvements made to institutional frameworks, a skilled labor force with expanded tertiary education, better innovation infrastructures, a deeper integration with global credit investment and trade markets, and a sophisticated business community—even if progress on these dimensions is not uniform across their economies.

The second category (Underperformer relative to GDP): it contains the countries that are not leaders neither learners. It contains the countries that are inefficient innovators such as Algeria, Iran and others.

5. Conclusion:

Nowadays, innovation faces huge change due to its importance in the different sectors. In addition, it is touched in all countries with different levels of incomes but with different rates. In addition, following the different procedures followed in the different countries especially the one that make the Sub-African Countries learners of innovation following the latest figures, the most important ways to foster the innovation outputs are creating an effective environment for innovation and exploit it. Also, create and develop the national system of innovation, invest in human capital by improving the skilled labor force with expanded tertiary education. Because, the human capital is the essence of the change in the society, unleash the creative thinking to solve problems and lead the universities and the research establishments to attract and actively encourage the best and brightest minds from around the world, and generous funding opportunities to create various cycles in which the best minds seek the best mentors. Also, create better innovation infrastructure and a strong national innovation system based on well-linked innovation ecosystem, improve the institutional framework. Create the research centers to enhance the R&D in all fields because the quality of innovation is related with the studies and researchers. Create policies to attract skilled workers and

technology-intensive companies as the policies in Dubai where they get growth of the clusters of the innovative companies (Soumitra Dutta 2007, 28). Following the study of (Soumitra Dutta 2007, 28), the response of the country to the innovation is related with some important points such as: “The ability to adopt and benefit from leading technologies, increased human capacities, organizational and operational developments, and enhanced institutional performance”. Enhance the telecommunication sector because it is the key role to play in promoting innovation and in supporting the country’s evolution towards a knowledge-based economy. Facilitating the mobility of the people across the world because it is an important factor for the innovation and knowledge spillover

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